

SPHERES OF COMMUNICATION AND GENRES OF RUSSIAN AND UZBEK ELOQUENCE

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Abstract: The article explores the art of oratory in the context of Russian and Uzbek cultures. The main focus is on the genres of oratory, their historical development, modern trends, and the influence of technology on this form of art. The author emphasizes the importance of preserving and developing oratory in the modern world and offers perspectives for further study of the topic.

Keywords: oratory, Russian culture, Uzbek culture, historical development, modern trends, technology, genres, communication.

Eloquence is certainly one of the most expressive and powerful arts of mankind. It's not just the ability to speak beautifully and persuasively; it is the art of speaking that combines a deep understanding of language, psychology and culture. A speaker who knows the art of eloquence can not only convey his thought, but also inspire, motivate, convince, or even change the worldview of his listeners.

Since ancient times, eloquence has played a central role in public life. Whether it was ancient Greek agoras, Roman senates, or royal courts, orators used their skills to shape public opinion, influence political decisions, and even determine historical events.

In today's world, where boundaries are blurred and cultures collide and mix, eloquence is even more relevant. Each culture has its own unique traditions and styles of eloquence that reflect its historical, social and cultural values. Understanding and respecting these differences is the key to successful intercultural communication.

Thus, the study of the genres of eloquence and their application in different cultural contexts not only enriches our understanding of the world, but also helps to create more harmonious and mutually understanding relationships between people of different cultures.

Eloquence, as the art of public speaking, has deep roots in the history of many peoples, including Russia and Uzbekistan. This is an art that reflects the cultural, social and political characteristics of each era.

In Uzbekistan, the art of eloquence was closely associated with literary works. Authors such as Mahmud Kashgari and Yusuf Khas Hajib made significant contributions to the development of eloquence in the region. Their works, such as "Devonu lugatit-turk" and "Kutadgu bilig", are not only masterpieces of literature, but also reflect a deep understanding of the art of speech [1]. These works serve as an example of how eloquence can be used to express cultural identities and values.

In Russia, eloquence also has a rich history. It has evolved over the centuries, reflecting the various stages of the country's historical and cultural development. From ancient Slavic epics to the speeches of Russian tsars and emperors, eloquence was a tool of power, education and culture. In different historical periods, it has adapted to socio-cultural changes, reflecting the spirit of the time and national characteristics.

It is important to note that eloquence in both countries was not an isolated phenomenon. It was closely connected with global trends and interacted with the eloquence of other cultures and peoples. For example, during the Renaissance and Enlightenment, Russian eloquence was influenced by Western European traditions, while Uzbek eloquence interacted with Persian and Arabic cultures.

Eloquence, as the art of public speaking, plays an important role in various areas of communication.

Public speaking and its role in society: Public speaking is a key element in education, politics and culture. They allow individuals to express their opinions, share knowledge and influence public opinion. Successful public speaking requires not only deep knowledge, but also the ability to interact with the audience, which is confirmed by the work of K. Krupiei [2].

Educational: lectures, discussions, debates: In the educational field, eloquence is used to convey knowledge, stimulate critical thinking, and discuss ideas. Lectures, discussions and debates are the main forms of the educational process, where the art of speech plays a central role.

Arts and culture: theater, cinema, literature: In the field of art and culture, eloquence is used to express emotions, ideas and cultural values. From theatrical monologues to cinema and literature, the art of speaking allows artists and writers to engage with audiences on a deep emotional level.

Political arena: Leadership speeches, political debate: In the political arena, eloquence is used to shape public opinion, influence voters, and debate key issues. Leaders' speeches and political debates often become decisive factors in political campaigns [3].

Like any art, eloquence has evolved and changed over time. In different historical periods, it reflected the socio-cultural, political and economic realities of the era, adapting to them and influencing them.

Eloquence, as the art of expressive expression, has various genres that reflect the cultural and historical characteristics of each country.

The main genres of Russian eloquence:

- Oratory: This genre covers public speeches, speeches and lectures that are aimed at informing, persuading or inspiring the audience.

- Poetic eloquence: This is an expressive art that uses poetry to convey emotions, ideas, and cultural values.

- Prose eloquence: In this genre, the emphasis is on narrative style, which may include stories, anecdotes, and stories.

The main genres of Uzbek eloquence:

- Folk eloquence: This genre is based on traditional Uzbek folk stories, songs and poems that are passed down from generation to generation [4].

- Classical eloquence: It includes the works of famous Uzbek authors such as Mahmud Kashgari and Yusuf Khas Khajib, who have made a significant contribution to the development of eloquence in the region.

- Modern eloquence: This genre reflects contemporary trends and influences, and adapts traditional forms of eloquence to modern conditions.

- Each of these genres has its own unique features and style, which reflect the cultural, social and historical contexts of Russia and Uzbekistan.

Eloquence, as the art of expressive utterance, has its own unique genres and features in different cultures. Consider the similarities and differences in the genres of eloquence of the Russian and Uzbek languages:

Similarities:

Oratory: In both cultures, oratory plays an important role in public speaking, lectures, and discussions.

Traditional Roots: Both Russian and Uzbek eloquence have deep traditional roots that reflect the historical and cultural characteristics of each country [5].

Adaptation to modern times: Over time, both languages have adapted their genres of eloquence to modern conditions, including the impact of globalization and technological change.

Differences:

Poetic and prose eloquence: In Russian culture, there is a clear division between poetic and prose eloquence, while in Uzbek culture this division may be less pronounced.

Folk and classical eloquence: Uzbek eloquence has unique genres, such as folk and classical eloquence, which reflect the cultural and historical characteristics of the region [6].

Cultural and historical factors play a key role in shaping the genres of eloquence. For example, religious and philosophical traditions, as well as historical events such as wars and revolutions, influenced the development of eloquence in Russia and Uzbekistan [7].

Social factors such as education, economics, and politics also influence the genres of eloquence and their development in both cultures.

The modern world, saturated with technology and social networks, has a significant impact on the art of eloquence. Consider the main trends:

The impact of technology and social networks on eloquence:

Digital platforms: With the advent of online platforms such as Zoom, Skype, and others, opportunities for public speaking have become more accessible. Speakers can now reach a global audience without the need for a physical presence.

Social media: Platforms like YouTube, TikTok and Instagram provide new formats for speakers to express their ideas and engage with the audience. Short videos, vlogs, and streams have become popular formats for public speaking.

Adaptation of traditional genres of eloquence to modern conditions:

Interactivity: Modern speakers actively use interactive elements such as polls, chats, and Q&A sessions to engage the audience in dialogue.

Visual aids: Presentations, infographics and multimedia elements have become an integral part of modern eloquence, making it more visual and attractive.

Adapting to cultural differences: In an era of globalization, speakers are faced with the need to adapt their speeches to different cultural and linguistic contexts.

Modern technologies and social networks provide speakers with new opportunities and challenges. However, the basic principles of eloquence, such as clarity, persuasiveness, and emotional connection with the audience, remain unchanged.

In today's rapidly changing world, filled with technology and digital communication, the art of eloquence remains relevant and important. Even though modern technologies provide us with many new ways to communicate, the basic principles of eloquence, such as the ability to persuade, inspire and create an emotional connection with the audience, remain unchanged. They play a key role in education, politics, business and culture. The art of eloquence continues to develop and adapt to modern conditions. Exploring this topic can lead to new methods and approaches to help speakers interact effectively with audiences in the digital age.

In addition, a comparative analysis of the eloquence of different cultures can provide valuable lessons on how different peoples express their ideas and values.

In conclusion, the art of eloquence remains one of the most powerful communication tools. Its preservation and development in the modern world will not only enrich our culture, but also help us to better understand each other.

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